

Acknowledgement

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3-Hydroxypyridine-2-thiol, a Reagent for the Spectrophotometric Determination of Osmium

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THIOUREA¹⁻³, along with several of its derivatives⁴⁻⁷ has long been used for the spectrophotometric determination of osmium. The complexation between these reagents and osmium is attributed to the presence of a thioketo group (C = S) linked to -NH or -NHR. Recently some more reagents⁸⁻¹¹ have also been suggested for the purpose. Most of the methods suffer from the disadvantage of the interference due to associated platinum metals and require a rigid control of the working conditions. To improve upon the rather limited success of these reagents, in this paper is reported the use of a new reagent 3-hydroxypyridine-2-thiol (HPT), which behaves as a selective and sensitive reagent and allows the determination of osmium(VIII) in micro amounts even in the presence of platinum and other base metals. This reagent (HPT) has already been used for the spectrophotometric and chelatometric determination of iron¹².

In strong hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide media, osmium(VIII) forms with the reagent two complexes, a brown ($\lambda_{\max} = 470$ nm) and a red ($\lambda_{\max} = 520$ nm), both being non-extractable in the commonly used organic solvents. The complexation takes place in cold. The non-interference of EDTA in the colour reaction allows the determination of osmium in the presence of many foreign ions.

Experimental

Apparatus and Reagents

A Unicam Spectrophotometer SP 600 was used for absorbance measurements and a Metrohm pH

meter was employed for measuring the pH's of the solutions.

A standard solution of osmium(VIII) was obtained from its tetroxide as described by Ayres and Wells¹³, which was further standardized by the method of Klobbie¹⁴. The reagent solution was obtained by dissolving an appropriate quantity in ethanol. This was kept in Corning bottles wrapped in black papers and they were stored in a refrigerator. Standard solutions of other cations were prepared from their chlorides or nitrates and of anions from their sodium or potassium salts; the strengths were determined by conventional methods.

All other reagents were of the highest chemical purity.

Recommended Procedure

To a suitable aliquot of osmium solution, add 2 ml of HPT solution ($10^{-2}M$), adjust the acidity or alkalinity of the solution to 3N and after raising the volume to 10 ml, measure the absorbance of the complexes at the respective $\lambda_{\max}$'s of the complexes using water blanks. Osmium content is determined by comparing it with the standard calibration curves.

Results and Discussion

Absorbance spectra and effect of acidity and alkalinity

The absorption spectra of the system was taken by taking a fixed amount of osmium and excess of reagent solution and varying the pH of solutions to different levels. It was observed that from pH 1-7, a brown complex, exhibiting maximum extinction at 470 nm was obtained. From pH 7-11, a red complex, having $\lambda_{\max}$ at 520 nm was formed. However, no constancy in absorbance could be obtained between these two pH ranges. Hence, the effect of HCl and NaOH concentrations was studied in detail.

It was seen that in case of both complexes the absorbances remains constant and maximum when acidity (for brown complex) and alkalinity (for red complex) ranges are 1-6N HCl and NaOH respectively. Subsequent studies were, therefore, carried out at 3N HCl and 3N NaOH concentrations. Absorption spectra were taken against water blank as the reagent does not absorb at the working wavelengths ($\lambda_{\max}$'s of the complexes).

Effect of heating time and stability

Heating decreases the absorbance of the coloured complexes and was, therefore, avoided. The absorbance of the complexes was found to remain constant for at least 12 hours after which it slowly starts decreasing.

Order of addition of reagents

Variation in the order of the reactants did not have any effect. However, the order followed during the course of investigations is osmium solution, interfering ions (if any), HPT and NaOH or HCl to maintain the required alkaline and acidic conditions.

Reagent concentration, Beer's law, optimum range and sensitivity of the colour reaction

To a fix amount of osmium solution, were added different amounts of the reagent solution. Acidity or alkalinity of the solutions was adjusted to 3*N* by means of HCl or NaOH and the total volume was made upto 10 ml. Extinction of the two complexes was recorded at their respective λ_{max} 's. The results (Table 1) revealed that a slightly different amount of the reagent are required for the two complexes to attain maximum absorbance. However, in the subsequent studies 20 molar excess of the reagent has been added to ensure the complete complexation. Validity of Beer's law was examined at the various working conditions and from this data sensitivities (in terms of Sandell's definition^{1b}) and optimum working range, leading to the accurate determination of the metal, has also been calculated (Table 1).

Composition and nature of the complexes

Composition of the complexes was ascertained by applying two methods viz., method of continuous variations and mole ratio method. Both the methods confirmed that, in complexes, osmium combined with HPT in the ratio of 1 : 2 (Table 1).

of these observations, no tentative structures could be proposed.

Effects of foreign ions

To carry out determination in the presence of various ions (anions and cations), added excess of HPT solution to a solution containing osmium and diverse ion and the recommended procedure was followed. Tolerance limits were taken to be the amounts in γ/ml which do not cause an error of more than $\pm 2\%$.

The following results were obtained when determinations were carried out in 3*N* HCl and 3*N* NaOH media (tolerance limits being given in parentheses)

Studies in 3*N* HCl

Fluoride, oxalate, borate, citrate, nitrate(500), phosphate (300); persulphate, nitrite, bromide (100), iodide (350); cyanide (80); ruthenium(III), rhodium (III), palladium(II), and iridium(IV) (5); platinum (IV), copper(II), lead(II), nickel(II), cobalt(II) (10); zinc(II), manganese(II) (20); mercury(II), scandium (III), molybdenum(VI), tin(IV), cadmium(II), indium (III) (25); barium(II), lanthanum(III), uranium(VI) (50); EDTA (1100).

Studies in 3*N* NaOH

Fluoride, iodide, cyanide, persulphate (100); oxalate, borate (500); tartrate, citrate, phosphate, nitrite, bromide (250); ruthenium(III), rhodium(III), palladium(II), iridium(IV), ferric*(III) (5); platinum(IV), copper*(II), nickel*(II), cobalt*(II) (10); lanthanum*(III), magnesium(II), uranium(VI), barium(II), zinc(II) (50); tin*(IV), cadmium(II) and mercury*(II) (25), manganese*(II), molybdenum(VI), indium*(III) (30), scandium(III) (40); lead*(II) (20); EDTA (1100).

Masking and determination in synthetic mixtures

It can be seen from the table that 100-fold of EDTA do not cause any alteration in the absorbance. To add to utility of the method developed, EDTA has been successfully employed as a masking agent to circumvent the interferences caused by the following cations, the amounts (γ/ml) being given in parenthesis :

Ru³⁺(50); Rh³⁺(50); Pd²⁺(50); Ir³⁺(50); Pt⁴⁺(100); Cu²⁺(50); Ni²⁺(80); Co²⁺(100); Al³⁺(50) and Pb²⁺(50).

As naturally occurring ores of osmium are not easily available, different synthetic mixtures almost similar in composition to these ores, were prepared and amount of osmium was determined as follows :

To the various synthetic mixtures added EDTA (3 cc, 10⁻²*M*) and excess of HPT and followed the recommended procedure. The osmium content is determined from the calibration curves drawn under the similar conditions. The results show that osmium can be accurately determined in the presence of other platinum metals with which it is usually associated.

TABLE I—CHARACTERISTICS OF COMPLEXES

Characteristics	Os-HPT Complex, studies at 3 <i>N</i> HCl concentration	Os-HPT Complex, studies at 3 <i>N</i> NaOH concentration
Colour	Brown	Red
λ_{max}	470 nm	520 nm
Sandell's sensitivity	0.020 γ Os/cm ²	0.058 γ Os/cm ²
Molar absorptivity	9.51 $\times 10^3$	3.28 $\times 10^3$
HPT needed for full colour development	10-Molar concentration	15-Molar concentration
Acidity or alkalinity range to attain maximum absorbance	1-6 <i>N</i> HCl concentration	1-6 <i>N</i> NaOH concentration
Molar composition (metal : HPT)	1 : 2	1 : 2
Adherence to Beer's law	19.20 γ/ml	17.30 γ/ml
Optimum range for accurate determination	3.50 to 13.40 γ/ml	4.20 to 14.80 γ/ml
Nature of Complex	Anionic	Anionic

Non-extractability of the complexes into any organic solvents of common use, showed their ionic nature. This observation was further substantiated by the fact that the solutions of complexes were retained almost completely by an anionic resin (Amberlite IR 400, Chloride form) and they passed unchanged through the cationic resin, showing thereby the anionic nature. However, only on the basis

* Got precipitated and removed by centrifugation.

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Synthesis of Some 3-phenanthryl Keto-Anils

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THE anils have been synthesised by different workers¹⁻⁵ but those derived from glyoxals and aryl amines have not been investigated comprehensively. These compounds have been reported¹¹⁻¹⁴ to be chelating agents for various transition elements. Therefore, a systematic study in the preparation of 3-phenanthryl anils was undertaken.

In the present communication preparation of nineteen new 3-phenanthryl anils have been narrated (Table 1). These anils were prepared by refluxing the reactants in glacial acetic acid except those at sl. no. 14, 15, 16, 18 and 19. These compounds showed a typical behaviour finally giving a tarry

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF 3-PHENANTHRYL ANILS AND DERIVATIVES

Sl. no.	R	Colour and crystal form	Yield %	M.P.°C			λ_{max} Pri.	(nm) for	
				Anil	Oxime	Semi-carbazone		> C=O	> C=N Sec.
1.	H	L.B. plates	80	85	137	157	240	—	211
2.	2-CH ₃	G.Y. plates	83	138	113	135	267	293	222
3.	3-CH ₃	O. needles	75	131	123	147	268	295	221
4.	4-CH ₃	O. needles	86	140	133	152	267	294	221
5.	2-NO ₂	Y. plates	72	128	161	159	295	320	277
6.	3-NO ₂	Buff globules	76	103	120	146	297	321	267
7.	4-NO ₂	Y. plates	69	115	127	123	294	319	270
8.	2-OH	Grey needles	82	220	114	143	296	340	284
9.	3-OH	G.Y. needles	71	261D	205	198	280	297	267
10.	2-OCH ₃	G.Y. plates	84	103-4	111	151	296	314	271
11.	4-OCH ₃	O. globules	98	122	146	153	294	—	263
12.	2-Cl	Y. plates	60	91	101	118	295	316	269
13.	3-Cl	Y. needles	78	141	112D	127	296	—	267
14.	4-N(CH ₃) ₂	B. needles	77	79	197	126D	275	—	253
15.	5 : 6-benzo	B. globules	73	224	201	213	296	—	271
16.	3 : 4-benzo	Y. needles	75D	188	159	162	280	295	265
17.	OH-2 : 3-benzo-4-SO ₂ H	G. needles	81	95	116	—	294	317	277
18.	p-phenylenediamine	O. plates	93	—	—	—	—	345	257
19.	m-phenylenediamine	O. plates	89	208	136	143	270	292	258

L = light; B = brown; G = greenish; O = orange; Y = yellow; D = decompose.

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